

ISic3206

I.Sicily inscription 3206

Language

Latin

Type

honorific;

dedication

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Found in theatre; from forum (?)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di
Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]us

2. [---]vus

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493968

EDR 139558

EDCS 22200387

Bibliography

Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 40
Mazzarino, S. 1980. Antico, tardoantico ed èra costantiniana, vol. 2. *Storia e civiltà*. Castello. At 355

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic3206. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4357232>